

Complex Quantum Entropy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 12, 2026

In (1) (from 2016), a complex quantum entropy is introduced as: $S \text{ density} = - 2 \ln(W) W^*W$, where $W(\mathbf{r} \text{ vector})$ is the wavefunction. We note that in the single particle bound case for which $W^*=W$, that this entropy is $-2 \int W W \ln(W) = - \int W W \ln(WW)$ which is the well-known Shannon's result for spatial quantum entropy. (We note that there is usually also a momentum entropy $-\int a(p)a(p) \ln(a^*(p)a(p))$ which is not included in (1), but it is possible that one wishes to focus on spatial entropy alone).

In previous notes (2) (from 2021), we introduced a complex quantum entropy $- \int W \ln(W)$ in order to calculate the free particle quantum wavefunction through the MaxEnt procedure. We then maximized this subject to the constraint $\int -ikx W(x)$ in order to obtain $\exp(ikx)$.

Here we try to show that the complex entropy of (1) is the same as that of (2), when one links (2) to the single particle bound state spatial entropy $-\int W^*W \ln(W^*W)$.

Complex Quantum Entropy

In (1), a complex quantum entropy is presented as:

$$S \text{ density} = - \int W^*(\mathbf{r} \text{ vector}) W(\mathbf{r} \text{ vector}) 2 \ln(W) \quad ((1))$$

For $W=W^*$, as in a quantum single particle bound state, one has

$$- \int W W \ln(WW) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is the usual Shannon's entropy for spatial probability, with momentum probability $a^*(p)a(p)$ left out. In other words, one should also have a momentum entropy

$$- \int a^*(p)a(p) \ln\{a^*(p)a(p)\} \quad ((3))$$

We assume here, however, that (1) wishes to focus on spatial entropy alone and so do not consider momentum entropy density.

Complex Entropy for Calculating $\exp(ipx)$

In (2), we introduced a Shannon's entropy and maximized it subject to the constraint $\int ikx W$ in order to find the solution:

$$W(x) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((4)) \text{ from } \text{Maximization of } - \int W \ln(W) + ikx W \quad ((5))$$

The form ((5)) mimics that of Maxwell-Boltzmann maximization with ikx instead of e_i (single particle energy) and W instead of $p(e_i)$. W for the free particle is a complex value $\exp(ipx)$ whereas usual probability is a real number. We argue that this is not a problem because one

may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ (part of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$) from conservation of p and E arguments. The probability is complex with a unit modulus because it applies to a free particle which is not part of an energy distribution etc., i.e. all free particles have the same real value weight, but differ in their contribution of momentum and energy (which does not affect their real value weight).

In particular, strict probability-conservation arguments (without MaxEnt) suggest that:

$$P1(E1)P1(E2) = P1(E1+E2) \quad \text{and} \quad P2(p1)P2(p2) = P2(p1+p2) \quad ((6))$$

Here $p1$ and $p2$ are momentum vectors pointing along the x axis. This would suggest $P1 = \exp(-E/C1)$ and $P2 = \exp(-p/C2)$ for unit considerations. Special relativistic invariance, however, leads to:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((7))$$

Thus, one may see a complex probability arise and a possible MaxEnt approach is given by ((5)).

We first note that ((5)) does not formally become $-W \ln(W)$ for W real as in the case of a single particle bound state. We note, however, that ((5)) is used strictly in a MaxEnt approach which is a variational approach. In such variational approaches involving wavefunctions in the literature, W^* is usually considered independent of W . Thus, one may multiply ((5)) (which already includes a Lagrange multiplier) by W^* because this function is not varied and does not change the solution. One may also multiply ((5)) by 2. Then:

$$-W \ln(W) \longrightarrow -2W^*W \ln(W) \quad ((8))$$

This is the solution of (1) and also represents Shannon's spatial entropy for $P(x) = WW$.

In other words, taking the entropy from (2) used in MaxEnt and multiplying by $2W^*$ yields the entropy of (1). Thus the two are equivalent as the result from (2) should in fact be multiplied by $2W^*$ to match spatial Shannon's entropy for a bound state, but W^* and 2 are not needed in the MaxEnt calculation.

We next consider maximizing the entropy given (1).

Given (1)'s formal expression of S density = $-W^*W^2 \ln(W)$, we consider maximizing this subject to the constraint:

$$-B W^* \frac{d}{dx} W \quad ((9)) \quad \text{which must yield a constant at each point } r \text{ vector}$$

We suggest that even though one takes the d/dx derivative in ((9)), the result must be evaluated at a fixed r vector point (which may be any r vector point). We argue that the Lagrange multiplier B may then in fact be a function of r vector which is consistent with our a priori choice of a Lagrange multiplier kx in ((5)). One has:

$$- \int B(r \text{ vector}) W^* d/dx W \text{ as a constraint } ((10))$$

If one wishes to calculate the free particle W , then one has the added constraint that $W^*W=1$ for every x point (W unnormalized). One should thus extremize

$$- \int \ln(W) + b_1 W^*W + b_2 W^* d/dx W \quad ((11))$$

Note: The 2 factor form (1) can be eliminated by changing the Lagrange multipliers.

$$\text{Then: } -1/W - b_2 dW^*/dx = 0 \quad ((12)) \text{ (here we treat } b_2 \text{ as a constant)}$$

One may remove W^*W linked to b_1 and set it to 1.

As argued above, we allow the Lagrange multiplier to depend on x because ((12)) is an equation that may be calculated at any x point. Here we treat W^* as independent of W . Given that we have used $W^*W=1$ throughout, we try a solution with $b_1=0$. Then

$$-W^* - b_2(x) dW^*/dx = 0 \quad ((13))$$

We try a solution of $W=\exp(ipx)$. Then: $-1 - b_2(x) p = 0$ or $b_2 = 1/p$ if b_2 is not a function of x ((14))

There is an alternative way, however, of considering the entropy of (1), i.e.

$$-2 \int W^*W \ln(W) \quad ((15))$$

One may remove 2 because it is linked with Lagrange multipliers and note that W^* is an independent function of W . Then one maximizes:

$$- \int W \ln(W) + b_1 W + b_2(x) dW/dx \quad ((16))$$

One may set $b_1=0$ as long as the solution leads to $W^*W=1$.

$$\text{This leads to: } -1 - \ln(W) - db_2/dx = 0$$

$$\text{If } W=\exp(ipx), \text{ then } -1 - ipx = db_2/dx \text{ or } b_2 = -x - .5 ipxx \quad ((17))$$

It is possible, however, to replace the constraint $W^* d/dx W$ with $b(x)k W^*W$ and pull out W^* . Then one has the method of (2).

We suggest that the complex entropy used in (1), at least when used in MaxEnt situations, is identical to that of (2). One may take the entropy of (2) $- \int W \ln(W)$ and multiply it by $2W^*$ (as W^* was the removed independent variable and 2 was removed due to Lagrange multipliers). Then one obtains $-2 \int W^*W \ln(W)$ for the single particle bound state. Thus, the complex entropy introduced in (2) is the same as that used in (1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, (1) introduces a complex entropy density of $-W^*W^2 \ln(W)$. In (2), we used the entropy $-W \ln(W)$ subject to a constraint $\int |x| W$ to find $\exp(ipx)$ (the free particle wavefunction) using MaxEnt. In such an approach, one may throw away W^* factors and constant factors as W^* is taken to be independent of W and constant factors may be adjusted by Lagrange multipliers. Thus, $-W \ln(W)$ from (2) should become $-2 W^*W \ln(W)$ when applied to a single particle bound state. A solution is then $-2 W^*W \ln(W)$ which is in fact the result of (1).

References

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<https://files01.core.ac.uk/download/pdf/81704074.pdf>
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